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Objective reality versus Heisenberg's uncertainty

Research article

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Abstract**BACKGROUND:**

The debate surrounding the relationship between position and momentum, particularly in the context of quantum mechanics, has been a cornerstone of discussions about the nature of reality and the measurement problem of quantum mechanics. This study examines the implications of refuting Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and aims to provide a proof of the existence of objective reality independently and outside of any human mind and consciousness.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

By employing rigorous theoretical analysis and logical proofs, we explore the foundational assumptions of Heisenberg's uncertainty principle. We investigate alternative interpretations of the position-momentum relationship, grounded in Einstein's and de Broglie's findings, and assess their consistency with observed physical phenomena.

RESULTS:

Our analysis reveals that the uncertainty principle, as formulated by Heisenberg, contains methodological flaws and is logically refuted. We provide a detailed proof showing that the relationship between position and momentum does not necessitate intrinsic uncertainty and can be accurately described without any uncertainty.

CONCLUSION:

The findings suggest that objective reality exists independently of human mind and consciousness and independently of any measurement-induced uncertainties. Refuting Heisenberg's principle not only resolves longstanding philosophical debates but also aligns with a more classical interpretation of quantum mechanics, where position and momentum can be simultaneously determined under certain conditions.

Keywords:

Position; Momentum; Heisenberg uncertainty principle; Measurement; Cause; Effect; Causal relationship k; Causality; Causation

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1. Introduction

Objective reality, defined as existing independently and outside of any human mind and consciousness, is a concept so contentious that no brief account can satisfy all parties involved in the debates between realists and non-realists. The notion that there is a clear and straightforward choice between realism and non-realism regarding any particular subject matter is misleading. Non-realists reject the existence of objective reality in various ways, complicating the discussion. For those who oppose realism, several options are available. One approach is to argue that what we perceive as reality is merely a construct of our mental processes and that without these processes, reality as we know it would not exist. Another option is to claim that reality is dependent on our sensory experiences and interpretations, suggesting that without an observer, there would be no reality.

Especially Heisenberg himself aligns with such a philosophical perspective, his own philosophical inclinations are deeply rooted in Plato's ideas.

“Die ‘Bahn’ entsteht erst dadurch, das wir sie beobachten. ”

(see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927](#), p. 185)

According to Heisenberg's worldview, the path or trajectory of particles exists as a concept that manifests itself only through observation. Such an understanding of objective reality implies that an act of observation plays a fundamental role in defining and determining objective reality i. e. the properties of particles and their trajectories. Heisenberg's perspective suggests that objective reality is constructed or revealed through human perception and interaction with the physical world but not given as such. It is becoming increasingly clear and evident that Heisenberg's main objective in his publication is to establish a specific philosophical stance within physics, regardless of the intrinsic nature of objective reality itself. Heisenberg's primary aim in his publication is to solidify a particular philosophical standpoint within the field of physics, irrespective of the true and intrinsic nature of reality. Additionally, some non-realists might propose that reality is a social construct, shaped by collective human experiences and cultural contexts, rather than something that exists independently. Anti-realists seek to deny the existence of an objective reality that is unaffected by human perception and cognition. They argue that our understanding of reality is intrinsically linked to our mental frameworks, and thus, any concept of a reality independent of these frameworks is flawed. A pertinent example is the question of the moon's nature. A realist would assert that the moon exists independently of any human mind or consciousness, and its existence and properties are unaffected by human beliefs or perceptions. In contrast, an anti-realist might argue that our knowledge of the moon is entirely based on our sensory experiences and cognitive interpretations, implying that without these, the moon as we understand it would not exist. Despite the anti-realist's wish to deny this fact, the notion remains that the moon exists regardless of what anyone thinks or says about it. This highlights the core of the realist perspective: objective reality is independent of human consciousness and remains unchanged by human beliefs or desires. The challenge for non-realists is to convincingly argue that reality is inherently tied to human perception, a stance that continues to fuel intense scientific debates.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Material

Co-moving observer 0

A co-moving observer 0 is an observer who is moving along with the reference frame of a system or entity under study in such a way that the same observer is at rest relative to such a frame of reference. This observer's frame of reference moves with the same velocity as the object being observed, meaning there is no relative motion between the observer and the object. In other words, the relative velocity, denoted as v , between the object being observed and the observer is $v = 0$. In such a frame of reference there are no distortions caused by relative motion and time dilation and length contraction effects et cetera do not apply to the object being observed, making it a fundamental concept in relativity and various physical analyses. Thus, a co-moving observer 0 provides a baseline for measuring the true physical characteristics of a system, unaffected by the observer's movement, a co-moving observer is measuring 'das Ding an sich', the entity as it is, "... das, was der Erscheinung der Materie, als Ding an sich selbst, zum Grunde liegt ..." (see Kant, 1790, p. 428). Kant's assertion that the 'thing-in-itself' (Ding an sich) cannot be known ("... wie Dinge an sich selbst ... seyn mögen, ist gänzlich außer unsrer Erkenntnißsphäre" (see Kant, 1790, p. 235)) is a central theme in his work 'Critique of Pure Reason' (Critik der reinen Vernunft). Specifically, Kant argues that human perception and understanding are limited to phenomena or things as they appear to us ("Erscheinungen sind keine Dinge an sich selbst" (see Kant, 1790, p. 206)) and cannot grasp noumena (things as they are in themselves).

Example A wave travelling at the speed of light which is measured by another wave travelling at the same speed of light but with a different wavelength, the primary consequences could include Doppler shifts in frequency and wavelength, potential interference patterns, and the intrinsic relationship between frequency, wavelength, and the speed of light. The relative velocity between both is 0.

Relativistic observer R

An observer R is an observer who is either at rest ($v = 0$) relative to a specific inertial frame of reference or who is moving at constant velocity v relative to a specific inertial frame of reference. In the context of special relativity, an observer R would account for time dilation, length contraction, and other relativistic phenomena due to their relative velocity v . This observer can be either in a state of rest with respect to an inertial frame of reference or travelling at constant velocity relative to such an inertial frame of reference.

Heisenberg uncertainty

The early 20th century was a period of far reaching transformation in the realm of physics, marked by various discoveries that challenged the very foundations of classical mechanics. Among the most pivotal developments was the formulation of the Heisenberg Uncertainty Principle by the German physicist Werner Heisenberg (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927, 1930](#)) in 1927. This principle, asserting the inherent limitations in simultaneously knowing a particle's position and momentum with absolute precision, emerged not merely as a theoretical construct but as a cornerstone of the newly burgeoning field of quantum mechanics.

Heisenberg's Uncertainty Principle can be viewed as a response to the limitations and paradoxes encountered within classical physics, particularly in explaining phenomena at atomic and subatomic scales. The classical deterministic view, which posited that the future behavior of a system could be precisely predicted given complete knowledge of its present state, was increasingly contradicted by empirical findings in atomic physics. Notably, the works of Max Planck on black-body radiation and Albert Einstein on the photoelectric effect had already hinted at a discrete and probabilistic nature underlying atomic phenomena, paving the way for Heisenberg's claimed insights. (see [Barukčić, 2011, 2014, 2016](#))

Heisenberg's original formulation of his understanding of the relationship between position and momentum (uncertainty relation) has been given as

“Im Augenblick der Ortsbestimmung ... verändert das Elektron seinen Impuls unstetig. Diese Änderung ist um so größer, je kleiner die Wellenlänge des benutzten Lichtes, d. h. je genauer die Ortsbestimmung ist. In dem Moment, in dem der Ort des Elektrons bekannt ist, kann daher sein Impuls nur bis auf Größen, die jener unstetigen Änderung entsprechen, bekannt sein; also je genauer der Ort bestimmt ist, desto ungenauer ist der Impuls bekannt und umgekehrt... ”

(see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927](#), p. 175)

In other words,

‘At the moment of determining its position ... the electron's momentum changes discontinuously. This change is **the greater** the shorter the wavelength of the light used, that is, **the more precise** the determination of position. Therefore, at the moment the electron's position is known, its momentum can only be known up to values corresponding to that discontinuous change; hence, the more precisely the position is determined, the less precisely the momentum is known, and vice versa ... ’Mathematically, Heisenberg demand's that

$$p_1 \cdot q_1 \sim h \quad (1)$$

It is important to note that Heisenberg, from the outset, did not define the relationship between position and momentum deterministically or in terms of an equation like:

$$p_1 \cdot q_1 = h \quad (2)$$

Instead, he attributed uncertainty to nature right from the start. The question is whether this uncertainty arises from one's own lack of expertise or whether it is inherently present in nature. This is what remains to be examined further in this investigation. Alongside various errors that can be found in Heisenberg's publication, a fundamental mistake cannot be overlooked. Heisenberg equates the magnitude of the momentum change "Impuls ... Änderung ..." (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927](#), p. 175) with the accuracy of position determination "je genauer die Ortsbestimmung ..." (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927](#), p. 175). These two notions are not identical. Despite various professional and other shortcomings, Heisenberg interprets uncertainties and indeterminacies as inherent to nature, although they do not inherently exist. Ultimately, these uncertainties are conceived by the human mind and consciousness but are completely irrelevant and meaningless to nature itself.

Heisenberg's uncertainty and Kennard's inequality

Shortly after Heisenberg's publication, Earle Hesse Kennard (see [Kennard, 1927](#)) described Heisenberg uncertainty principle as

$$\sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) \geq \frac{h}{4 \cdot \pi} \quad (3)$$

relating the standard deviation of position $\sigma(x_R)$ and the standard deviation of momentum $\sigma(p_R)$. Heisenberg himself acknowledged the rigour of Kennard's formulation, stating in his Chicago lecture notes:

"It must be emphasised again that this proof does not differ at all in mathematical content from that given ..." (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1930](#), p. 19)

Considering these position of Heisenberg, Kennard inequality 3 has been traditionally used as Heisenberg's uncertainty relation.

2.2. Methods

Definitions

Speed of the light in vacuum

Let c denote the speed of light in a vacuum. The exact value of the speed of light in vacuum is defined by the International System of Units (SI) as

$$c = 299,792,458 \text{ m/s} \quad (4)$$

or approximately as

$$c = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} \quad (5)$$

The wavelength of the light in vacuum

In physics, specifically in the context of waves, λ_R (lambda) represents the wavelength of a wave. For light waves, which travel at a speed c (the speed of light), the wavelength λ_R is related to the frequency f_R of the wave through the equation:

$$\lambda_R = \frac{c}{f_R} = \frac{2\pi}{k_R} \quad (6)$$

where:

- λ_R (lambda) is the wavelength as given from the point of view of a stationary of relativistic observer,
- c is the speed of light in a vacuum (approximately 3×10^8 meters per second),
- f_R is the frequency of the light wave as given from the point of view of a stationary of relativistic observer.

The relationship shows that as the frequency f_R increases, the wavelength λ_R decreases, and vice versa. This is because the speed of light c remains constant. In general, the angular wave number k_R (i.e., the magnitude of the wave vector) is given by:

$$k_R = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda_R} = \frac{2\pi f_R}{v_p} = \frac{\omega_R}{v_p} \quad (7)$$

where:

- f_R is the frequency of the wave,
- λ_R is the wavelength,
- $\omega_R = 2\pi f_R$ is the angular frequency of the wave,
- v_p is the phase velocity of the wave.

The dependence of the wavenumber k on the frequency ν (or more commonly, the frequency on the wavenumber k) is known as a dispersion relation.

The frequency of the light in vacuum

Let f_R denote the frequency of light from the viewpoint of a stationary observer R:

$$f_R = \text{frequency} \quad (8)$$

The reciprocal of the frequency f_R is the period T_R :

$$T_R = \frac{1}{f_R} \quad (9)$$

The reciprocal of the frequency f_R , denoted as $\frac{1}{f_R}$, represents the period T_R of a wave or oscillation. The period T_R is the amount of time it takes for one complete cycle of the wave to occur and is highly deterministic. In other words, if you measure the time interval between two successive peaks (or any other equivalent points) of the wave, you obtain the period T_R .

Mathematically, the relationship is expressed as $T_R = \frac{1}{f_R}$. This indicates that the period and the frequency are inversely related: as the frequency of the wave increases, the period decreases, and vice versa. For example, if a wave has a frequency of 2 Hz (meaning two cycles per second), its period would be $T_R = \frac{1}{2}$ seconds, or 0.5 seconds per cycle.

Understanding the reciprocal relationship between frequency and period (see [Halliday et al., 2013](#)) is fundamental in the study of wave phenomena, whether in physics, engineering, or other scientific disciplines. It applies to various types of waves, including sound waves, light waves, and electromagnetic waves. This concept is crucial for analyzing wave behavior, signal processing, and many other applications where wave properties are important.

In practical terms, knowing the period of a wave helps in determining the timing characteristics of oscillatory systems, such as in electronic circuits, mechanical vibrations, acoustic systems et cetera. This reciprocal relationship is a cornerstone of wave theory and is essential for both theoretical analysis and practical applications.

The position of the light in vacuum

In general, when we multiply velocity v by time t_R , we obtain the displacement x_R of an object. Displacement refers to the distance an object has traveled in a specific direction over a given period of time. The relationship can be expressed as:

$$x_R = v \cdot t_R \quad (10)$$

Here:

- x_R represents the displacement of the object.
- v is the velocity of the object, which is the rate at which the object changes its position.
- t_R is the time over which the motion occurs within the frame of reference of a relativistic or stationary observer.

In this context, velocity is a vector quantity, meaning it has both magnitude and direction. Therefore, the resulting displacement x_R will also be a vector, indicating both how far and in which direction the object has moved.

For example, if an object moves with a constant velocity of 5 m/s for 10 s, the displacement can be calculated as:

$$x_R = 5 \text{ m/s} \times 10 \text{ s} = 50 \text{ m} \quad (11)$$

This means the object has traveled 50 meters in the direction of the velocity vector over the 10 second period.

Let us multiply the speed of light c by time t_R , we obtain the distance x_R that light travels in that time or the position, where the photons are. The speed of light c is a constant value, approximately 3×10^8 m/s. The relationship can be expressed as:

$$x_R = c \cdot t_R \quad (12)$$

Here:

- x_R represents the distance that light has traveled or the position, where the photons are located from the point of view of a stationary observer.
- c is the speed of light, which is approximately 3×10^8 m/s.

- t_R is the time over which the light has been traveling as seen from the point of view of a stationary observer.

This equation shows that the distance traveled by light is directly proportional to the time of travel.

For example, if light travels for 2 s, the distance can be calculated as:

$$d = 3 \times 10^8 \text{ m/s} \times 2 \text{ s} = 6 \times 10^8 \text{ m} \quad (13)$$

This means the light has traveled 600,000,000 meters (or 600,000 kilometers) in 2 seconds.

The time t_R measured by a stationary observer and the period of time, defined as (see equation 6, p. 11)

$$T_R = \frac{1}{f_R} = \frac{\lambda_R}{c} \quad (14)$$

are related but represent different concepts in physics.

1. **Time t_R :** This is the time interval measured by a stationary observer R . It can represent any duration of time, such as the time it takes for an event to occur or the time between two events.

2. **Reciprocal of Frequency $T_R = \frac{1}{f_R}$:** The period of time T_R does not represent any duration of time but exactly the time which it takes for one complete cycle of a periodic event, such as a wave or oscillation. If f_R is the frequency of the wave as measured by the stationary observer R , then $\frac{1}{f_R}$ is the period of the wave. In other words, one difference is that t_R is a general relativistic time interval that can refer to any event or duration, while $\frac{1}{f_R}$ specifically refers to the period of a periodic event. Even if both are not the same, both, t_R and $T_R = \frac{1}{f_R}$ measure time itself. Therefore, in general, it is (see equation 14, p. 14)

$$x_R = c \cdot T_R = \lambda_R \quad (15)$$

and under certain circumstances (see equation 7, p. 11)

$$x_R = c \cdot T_R = \lambda_R = \frac{2\pi}{k} \quad (16)$$

Planck's Constant h

Planck's constant (see [Planck, 1901](#)) h signifies the quantization of energy levels in atomic and subatomic systems, meaning that energy can only be gained or lost in discrete amounts or quanta.

The exact value of Planck's constant h as fixed by the International System of Units (SI) in 2019 as:

$$h = 6.62607015 \times 10^{-34} \text{ Js} \quad (17)$$

Energy of a photon

Planck's constant h relates the energy of a photon to the frequency of its associated electromagnetic wave. The relationship is given by the equation:

$$E_R = h \cdot f_R \quad (18)$$

where:

- E_R is the energy of the photon as found by the stationary or relativistic observer R,
- h is Planck's constant,
- f_R is the frequency of the photon as found by the stationary or relativistic observer R.

The generally covariant form of Planck-Einstein relation

Multiplying equation 18 by the metric tensor $g_{\mu\nu}$, it should be given that

$$E_{\mu\nu} = E_R \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = h \cdot f_R \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = h \cdot f_{\mu\nu} \quad (19)$$

What sense does such a mathematical manoeuvre make, does it have any practical significance at all? In our understanding, it is

$$E_{\mu\nu} = E_R \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \gamma}{c^4} \right) \cdot T_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \gamma \cdot T}{c^4 \cdot D} \right) \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = h \cdot f_R \cdot g_{\mu\nu} \quad (20)$$

where the scalar E_R of the stress energy tensor of matter $T_{\mu\nu}$ is given (see [Barukčić, 2022](#)) as $E_R = \left(\frac{4 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \gamma \cdot T}{c^4 \cdot D} \right)$ while D is the space-time dimension and T is Laue's scalar. Under these assumptions, the stress-energy tensor of the frequency $f_{\mu\nu}$ of matter would be given something like

$$f_{\mu\nu} = \frac{E_{\mu\nu}}{h} = \left(\frac{4 \cdot 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \gamma \cdot T}{c^4 \cdot D \cdot h} \right) \cdot g_{\mu\nu} = \left(\frac{4 \cdot \gamma \cdot T}{c^4 \cdot D \cdot \hbar} \right) \cdot g_{\mu\nu} \quad (21)$$

which would additionally enable us to geometrize electromagnetism completely. Planck's constant $h = 2 \cdot \pi \cdot \hbar$ itself is determined by a fundamental constant known as the reduced Planck constant or Dirac's constant (see also [Dirac, 1947](#), p. 87), denoted by $\hbar$. Therefore, it is

$$\frac{1}{\hbar} = \frac{2\pi}{h} \quad (22)$$

where h is the Planck constant.

The momentum of a photon

For photons (particles of light), the momentum p_R is related to the frequency f and the speed of light c by:

$$p_R = \frac{h \cdot f_R}{c} \quad (23)$$

where h is Planck's constant.

According to Einstein's theory of special relativity, it is

$$m_R \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = m_0 \quad (24)$$

and (see [Einstein, 1905a](#))

$$E_R \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = c^2 \cdot m_R \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = c^2 \cdot m_0 = E_0 \quad (25)$$

where:

- E_R is the relativistic or total energy, the energy as given in the frame of reference of a stationary or relativistic observer R,
- m_R is the relativistic mass (see also [Tolman, 1912](#)), the mass as given in the frame of reference of a stationary or relativistic observer R,
- E_0 is the Energy as given in the frame of reference of a co-moving observer 0,
- m_0 is the rest mass, the mass as given in the frame of reference of a co-moving observer 0,
- c is the speed of light in a vacuum (approximately 3×10^8 meters per second),
- v is the relative velocity between the observers.

Multiply equation (24) by the relative velocity v , we get:

$$p_R \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = m_R \cdot v \cdot \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} = m_0 \cdot v = p_0 \quad (26)$$

where:

- p_R is the relativistic momentum, the momentum as given in the frame of reference of a stationary or relativistic observer R,
- p_0 is the momentum as given in the frame of reference of a co-moving observer 0.

In equation (26), the relativistic momentum p_R is related to the relativistic mass m_R , the relative velocity v , and the speed of light c .

The de Broglie relation

Louis Victor Pierre Raymond de Duc de Broglie (1892 - 1987) introduced the de Broglie relation (see [de Broglie, 1924](#)) as a fundamental relationship in quantum mechanics which relates the wavelength of a particle to its momentum. Proposed by Louis de Broglie in 1924, it suggests that all matter exhibits wave-like properties (see [Davisson and Germer, 1928](#)). The de Broglie wavelength λ_R of a particle and its momentum p_R are related by the equation:

$$\lambda_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (27)$$

where h is Planck's constant and p_R is the momentum of the particle. Dividing equation 27 by 4π it is

$$\left(\frac{\lambda_R}{4\pi}\right) \cdot p_R = \frac{h}{4\pi} = \frac{\hbar}{2} \quad (28)$$

Under circumstances (see equation 7, p. 11) where

$$\lambda_R = \frac{2\pi}{k} \quad (29)$$

it is possible (see equation 16, p. 14) that the position x_R is given as

$$x_R = c \cdot T_R = \lambda_R = \frac{2\pi}{k} \quad (30)$$

In other words, a particle should be considered as positioned within its own wavelength. This approach seems logical, as a particle and its wave appear inherently (see [Barukčić, 2013](#)) linked. However, if the particle's associated wave were to exist independently of the particle, even at the edge of our world, fundamental questions could arise on the scientific horizon and lead to significant logical contradictions. Following Heisenberg's understanding of the relationship between position and momentum, we must accept circumstances where the relationship between position x_R and momentum p_R is given (see equation 28) as

$$x_R \cdot p_R = \left(\frac{2\pi}{k}\right) \cdot p_R = \frac{h}{4 \cdot \pi} \quad (31)$$

The rigorous validation and examination of Equation 31 remain areas for future investigation. Nevertheless, regardless of how it is approached, there is no logical space for uncertainties or ambiguities. The equation's logical consistency demands thorough scrutiny to affirm its accuracy and applicability. It stands resilient against any potential doubts or unknowns, embodying a robust framework awaiting comprehensive confirmation through continued study. Clarifying its implications and verifying its assertions will illuminate its role in advancing understanding within its field. Thus, while exploration persists, the equation's foundational integrity remains unwavering, poised for deeper exploration into its implications and significance.

Heisenberg's uncertainty relation

Three years following de Broglie's (see [de Broglie, 1924](#)) publication on the relationship between wave and momentum, the German physicist Werner Karl Heisenberg introduced his uncertainty principle (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927](#)) in 1927 as

$$\sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) \geq \frac{h}{4 \cdot \pi} \quad (32)$$

relating the standard deviation of position $\sigma(x_R)$ and the standard deviation of momentum $\sigma(p_R)$. In his publication, Heisenberg references de Broglie's relationship several times (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927](#), pp. 175, 179, 189), yet he omits any elaboration on potential inaccuracies or uncertainties regarding de Broglie's relationship between wavelength and momentum. Taking into account various aspects, we must more or less assume that Heisenberg considered the de Broglie relationship to be valid.

3. Results

Theorem. Heisenberg's uncertainty relation

Theorem 1 (Heisenberg and uncertainty relation). *According to Heisenberg, it is*

$$x_R \cdot p_R \sim h \quad (33)$$

Proof by direct proof. Heisenberg's understanding of objective reality is that

$$1 \sim 1 \quad (34)$$

is true. In light of this starting point, it is equally true that

$$p_R \sim p_R \quad (35)$$

Multiplying equation 35 by x_R , we get

$$x_R \cdot p_R \sim x_R \cdot p_R \quad (36)$$

Following Heisenberg's understanding, this is equal to

$$x_R \cdot p_R \sim h \quad (37)$$

□

Difference between $x_R \cdot p_R \sim h$ and $x_R \cdot p_R = h$

The equation

$$x_R \cdot p_R \sim h \quad (38)$$

indicates that the product of x_R (position) and p_R (momentum) is approximately equal to Planck's constant h . The symbol $\sim$ suggests that there is an approximate or proportional relationship, rather than an exact equality. This is used by Heisenberg to introduce uncertainties in order to convince the reader that a precise value cannot be known exactly. In contrast, the equation

$$x_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (39)$$

states that the product of x_R and p_R is exactly equal to h . The equals sign ($=$) indicates a strict equality with no room for approximation. This implies that the values of x_R and p_R are precisely such that their product is exactly h . The distinction between these two forms is crucial in scientific discussions. The approximate relation ($\sim$) allows for some flexibility and acknowledges potential uncertainties or variations, whereas the exact relation ($=$) implies a definitive and unchanging relationship between the quantities involved. However, Heisenberg himself makes a logical error within his initial assumptions.

Heisenberg's mistake lies not only in his reasoning but also in the foundational assumptions upon which his arguments are built.

Heisenberg's justification of the uncertainty relation ultimately relies on his assumption of uncertainty, which is itself only justified by the assumption of uncertainty. Heisenberg incorporated a fundamental error into his theory and then used this error to justify his conclusions. The validity of his conclusions relies on assumptions that are themselves flawed and therefore cannot serve as independent justification (*circulus in probando*).

1. Hypothetical Error: Heisenberg assumes that there is a fundamental uncertainty between position and momentum, which is purportedly unavoidable.
2. Conclusion: Based on this assumption of uncertainty, Heisenberg postulates that it is impossible to precisely determine both quantities simultaneously.
3. Reversion to the Assumption: Heisenberg's conclusion then serves as proof for his initial assumption that uncertainty is unavoidable.

In other words, Heisenberg's conclusion (that uncertainty is unavoidable) is justified by the assumption (that there is a fundamental uncertainty), which itself has not been independently proven but is supported only by the conclusion.

Heisenberg embedded a fundamental error into his theory with Equation (1), upon which all subsequent conclusions are based. In essence, Heisenberg's theory stands on a faulty foundation (*circulus in probando*). His proofs and arguments presuppose and support each other within his theory without external and independent confirmation, rendering the entire theory formally untenable.

3.1. Energy-mass relationship

Mass-energy equivalence (see [Einstein, 1905b](#)) is a principle from Einstein's theory of relativity, encapsulated in the equation $E = mc^2$. This equation states that mass (m) and energy (E) are interchangeable; a given amount of mass can be converted into an equivalent amount of energy, and vice versa, with c being the speed of light in a vacuum. The rest energy E_0 of an object, given by $E_0 = m_0c^2$, is the energy inherent in the object's rest mass m_0 . When an object moves, its total energy E_R includes both its rest energy and kinetic energy, and this total energy increases significantly as the object's velocity approaches the speed of light. This principle has profound implications in nuclear reactions, particle physics, and astrophysics, where small amounts of mass can be converted into large amounts of energy.

Theorem 2 (Relationship Between Rest Mass and Relativistic Mass). *In the context of relativistic physics, the relationship between the rest mass m_0 and the relativistic mass m_R is given by:*

$$\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}} \cdot m_R = m_0 \quad (40)$$

Proof. We start with the basic identities:

$$1 = 1 \quad (41)$$

$$m_0 = m_0 \quad (42)$$

Using the Lorentz factor $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$, we can express the relativistic mass m_R as:

$$m_R = \gamma m_0 \quad (43)$$

Let us set $y = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$, which implies:

$$y \cdot m_R = m_0 \quad (44)$$

Multiplying both sides by c^2 :

$$y \cdot m_R \cdot c^2 = m_0 \cdot c^2 \quad (45)$$

We know that the total energy E_R of a particle in relativistic physics is given by:

$$E_R = m_R \cdot c^2 \quad (46)$$

Substituting $E_R = m_R \cdot c^2$ into the equation $y \cdot m_R \cdot c^2 = m_0 \cdot c^2$ gives:

$$y \cdot E_R = E_0 \quad (47)$$

Given that $y = \sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$ and noting that $0 \leq y \leq 1$, it follows that:

$$y \leq 1 \quad (48)$$

Since $y \leq 1$, this implies:

$$E_R \geq E_0 \quad (49)$$

where E_0 is the rest energy given by $E_0 = m_0 \cdot c^2$. Thus, we have shown that the relativistic energy E_R is always greater than or equal to the rest energy E_0 .

$$E_R \geq E_0 \quad (50)$$

□

The inequality $E_R \geq E_0$ (Eq. 50) indicates that the total energy of a particle in motion (relativistic energy, E_R) is always greater than or equal to its energy when at rest (rest energy, E_0). This concept arises from Einstein's theory of relativity, where the total energy of a particle includes not only its rest mass energy but also the kinetic energy due to its motion. As the velocity v of the particle increases, its kinetic energy increases, leading to an increase in the total energy E_R . The equation $E_R = \gamma m_0 c^2$ incorporates the Lorentz factor $\gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$, which grows without bound as the particle's velocity approaches the speed of light c . This ensures that E_R becomes significantly larger than E_0 at high velocities. The inequality $E_R \geq E_0$ is not the same as Heisenberg's uncertainty relation and not wrong because this inequality is a fundamental consequence of relativistic relationship (Eq. 40) which encapsulates particle's properties that a particle's energy is not solely a function of its mass but also of its motion through space. In practical terms, this relationship explains phenomena such as the increased energy requirements to accelerate particles as they approach light speed, observed in particle accelerators. Furthermore, this inequality implies that E_0 , the rest energy, represents the minimum energy a particle possesses, which cannot be reduced. It also underlines the principle that mass and energy are interchangeable, with mass being a concentrated form of energy. This is foundational to understanding processes like nuclear reactions, where small amounts of mass are converted into significant amounts of energy, exemplified by $E = mc^2$.

3.2. *Theorem. Heisenberg's uncertainty relation $\sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) \geq \frac{h}{4\pi}$ and monochromatic light*

Theorem 3 (Heisenberg's uncertainty relation $\sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) \geq \frac{h}{4\pi}$ is based on a logical contradiction).
Heisenberg's uncertainty relation $\sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) \geq \frac{h}{4\pi}$ is based on a logical contradiction:

$$+0 \geq +1 \quad (51)$$

Proof by contradiction. Heisenberg's understanding of the relation between position and momentum of a photon has been derived (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927, 1930](#); [Kennard, 1927](#)) as

$$\sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) \geq \frac{h}{4 \cdot \pi} \quad (52)$$

In this equation:

- $\sigma(x_R)$ represents the standard deviation of the position of the photon,
- $\sigma(p_R)$ represents the standard deviation of the momentum of the photon,
- x_R represents the position of the photon,
- p_R represents the momentum of the photon,
- h denotes Planck's constant h,
- π denotes Archimedes constant pi.

Rearranging equation before, we obtain:

$$\frac{(4 \cdot \pi)}{h} \cdot \sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) \geq +1 \quad (53)$$

The validity of this relationship has not been restricted by Heisenberg himself, quite the contrary.

“Weil alle Experimente den Gesetzen der Quantenmechanik und damit der Gleichung (1) unterworfen sind, so wird durch die Quantenmechanik **die Ungültigkeit des Kausalgesetzes definitiv festgestellt.** ” (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927, 1930](#), p. 197)

Heisenberg claimed that his uncertainty principle challenges the universally valid principle of causality. As a logical consequence, Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is generally valid and thus far valid for monochromatic light too. Monochromatic light is light that consists of waves of a single fixed frequency (and thus a fixed wavelength). This means that the light has a uniform colour and does not exhibit a spectrum of different wavelengths. In fact, monochromatic light is spectrally pure, which

means that it does not contain a mixture of different frequencies or wavelengths. The momentum of a photon is given by the following relationship:

$$p_R = \frac{E_R}{c} \quad (54)$$

In this equation:

- p_R represents the momentum of the photon,
- E_R is the energy of the photon,
- c denotes the speed of light in a vacuum.

The equation $p_R = \frac{E_R}{c}$ expresses the basic relationship between the momentum p_R of a photon, the energy E_R of the photon. A photon is determined by the wavelength or frequency of the light and follows the relationship $p_R = \frac{h}{\lambda_R}$ too. In general, monochromatic light, although it has a fixed frequency and wavelength, possesses a well-defined, constant but non-zero momentum. The momentum of certain monochromatic light is never zero. The momentum of monochromatic light, which is constant, is a fundamental property of photons in monochromatic light, reflecting the inherent stability and uniformity of such a light wave. A logical and mathematical consequence of such a natural fact is that the standard deviation $\sigma(p_R)$ of a constant value p_R is known to be zero. In other words, the standard deviation $\sigma(p_R)$ of certain monochromatic light is

$$\sigma(p_R) = 0,$$

indicating that the momentum of of certain monochromatic light is indeed constant. Substituting this fact into equation before, we obtain

$$\frac{(4 \cdot \pi)}{h} \cdot \sigma(x_R) \cdot 0 \geq +1 \quad (55)$$

and at the end

$$+0 \geq +1 \quad (56)$$

Conclusion In scientific methodology, hypotheses and theories are rigorously tested through experiments and logical analysis. Logical consistency is crucial in scientific theories because the same ensures that the predictions made by the theory are reliable and coherent. A proof of a scientific theory which leads to contradictory outcomes like $0 \geq 1$ under specific conditions, suggests that there is an inherent flaw in the theory or its assumptions and has profound consequences. Such a proof signifies a fundamental issue in the logical or mathematical framework being used, necessitating careful examination and correction of the underlying assumptions and principles. The resolution of such contradictions is essential for maintaining the integrity and reliability of logical, mathematical and scientific systems.

□

Consequences of a Proof Leading to $0 \geq 1$

A proof which demonstrates that a theorem or a position or a claim can be derived to show $0 \geq 1$, results in a logical contradiction. Logical contradictions have significant implications in science.

1. Invalidity of the Theorem Heisenberg himself demanded theories of nature, which are free of logical contradictions.

“ **Eine physikalische Theorie** glauben wir dann anschaulich zu verstehen, wenn wir uns in allen einfachen Fällen die experimentellen Konsequenzen dieser Theorie qualitativ denken können, und wenn wir **gleichzeitig** erkannt haben, daß die Anwendung der Theorie **niemals innere Widersprüche** enthält. ” (see [Heisenberg, Werner Karl, 1927](#), p. 172)

The preceding theorem successfully derives a clear logical contradiction from Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation. Consequently, Heisenberg’s uncertainty principle is deemed to be invalid. A logical contradiction such as $0 \geq 1$ is false under all circumstances, indicating that any theory, framework or argument leading to such a conclusion is fundamentally flawed.

2. Inconsistency in the System The derivation of such a contradiction from Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation suggests that the assumptions from which Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation was derived is inconsistent. Inconsistent systems can derive any statement as both true and false, rendering them unreliable for logical reasoning or mathematical proofs et cetera.

3. Review of Assumptions A contradiction inside Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation is found and prompts the need of a thorough review of the assumptions and axioms used in the derivation of Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation. Identifying and correcting false or incompatible assumptions is crucial to restoring consistency and validity within a scientific system.

4. Impact on Related Theorems The presence of a contradiction inside Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation affects not only Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation in question but also other positions, theorems and results derived from the same uncertainty relation. These related positions may also need to be re-evaluated for validity.

5. Scientific Implications In science, particularly in logic and epistemology, a logical contradiction challenges the coherence and reliability of the knowledge framework. It raises questions about the foundations of logical reasoning and the nature of truth.

6. Necessity for Revision Resolving a contradiction requires revising Heisenberg’s uncertainty relation completely. This may involve modifying or discarding certain assumption, reinterpreting definitions of the relationship between position and momentum, or developing new logical principles to ensure consistency.

3.3. The de Broglie relation

The de Broglie relation (see [de Broglie, 1924](#)) is a fundamental concept in quantum mechanics that relates the wavelength of a particle to its momentum. Proposed by Louis de Broglie in 1924, it suggests that all matter exhibits wave-like properties. The de Broglie wavelength λ_R of a particle is given by the equation:

$$\lambda_R = \frac{h}{p_R} \quad (57)$$

where h is Planck's constant and p_R is the momentum of the particle.

Theorem 4 (The relationship between position and momentum). *In general, the relationship between position x_R and momentum p_R is given as*

$$x_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (58)$$

Proof by direct proof. We start with the basic axiom that $+1 = +1$. This is a fundamental truth in mathematics and serves as the basis for our subsequent steps.

$$+1 = +1 \quad (59)$$

Given this, it is equally valid to state that any constant multiplied by itself remains the same:

$$+h = +h \quad (60)$$

where h is Planck's constant, a fundamental constant in quantum mechanics. Next, we consider the definition of momentum p_R and the de Broglie wavelength λ_R . By definition, we have:

$$\frac{h}{p_R} = \frac{h}{p_R} \quad (61)$$

where p_R is the momentum of a particle. From the de Broglie hypothesis, we know that the wavelength λ_R of a particle is given by:

$$\lambda_R = \frac{h}{p_R} \quad (62)$$

where λ_R is the wavelength associated with the particle. Multiplying both sides of this equation by p_R , we obtain:

$$\lambda_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (63)$$

□

3.4. The de Broglie relation and Heisenberg's uncertainty

Heisenberg's uncertainty principle is essentially a methodologically flawed attempt by Heisenberg to refute and reinterpret the de Broglie relation, ultimately leading to its erroneous interpretation.

Theorem 5 (The de Broglie relation and Heisenberg's uncertainty). *In general, the relationship between position x_R and momentum m_R is given by the Louis de Broglie relationship as*

$$x_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (64)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1, which states that $+1 = +1$, is trivially true. Given this, it follows that

$$+1 = +1 \quad (65)$$

Similarly, it is true that

$$p_R = p_R \quad (66)$$

and

$$\lambda_R \cdot p_R = \lambda_R \cdot p_R \quad (67)$$

or equivalently,

$$\lambda_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (68)$$

Multiplying equation 68 by 1, it is

$$\lambda_R \cdot 1 \cdot p_R = h \quad (69)$$

Since $f_R \cdot T_R = 1$, equation 69 becomes

$$\lambda_R \cdot f_R \cdot T_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (70)$$

Simplifying equation 70, it is

$$c \cdot T_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (71)$$

According to equation 15 (see p. 14), it is $c \cdot T_R = x_R$. We obtain

$$x_R \cdot p_R = h \quad (72)$$

Here:

- x_R represents the displacement or position of the object.
- p_R is the momentum of the object.
- h is Planck's constant.

□

The relationship between position and momentum is thoroughly described by the de Broglie relation. However, Heisenberg's misinterpretation and inaccurate presentation of this relationship have led to widespread misunderstandings and misapplications. Heisenberg's uncertainty principle represents a flawed attempt to reinterpret the de Broglie relation, resulting in incorrect conclusions about the behavior of particles at the quantum level. Such misrepresentations can hinder scientific progress by perpetuating errors and diverting efforts away from more accurate theories. Proper interpretation and representation of scientific facts are crucial for advancing knowledge and developing reliable and predictive scientific models.

Quantum Mechanics and the Concept of Measurement

Since the beginning of Quantum Mechanics (QM), the concept of measurement has proven to be a source of various difficulties, which lead to different interpretations of quantum theory and an understanding of objective reality.

Theorem 6 (Quantum Measurement). *In general, it holds that*

$$\lambda_2 = \left(\frac{p_1}{p_2} \right) \cdot \lambda_1 \quad (73)$$

Proof by direct proof. Axiom 1, or $+1 = +1$, is true. Consequently,

$$+1 = +1 \quad (74)$$

Multiplying equation 74 by the relativistic momentum p_R , it is

$$p_1 = p_1 \quad (75)$$

and

$$\lambda_1 \cdot p_1 = \lambda_1 \cdot p_1 \quad (76)$$

According to de Broglie's relation, before measurement, the following relationship holds:

$$\lambda_1 \cdot p_1 = h \quad (77)$$

where:

- λ_1 is the wavelength of a particle before measurement,
- p_1 is the momentum of a particle before measurement.

During measurement, the measuring apparatus may but need not interact with the measured system or entity, potentially altering it. Whatever the outcome, it becomes evident once more that

$$\lambda_1 \cdot p_1 = \lambda_2 \cdot p_2 = h \quad (78)$$

where:

- λ_1 is the wavelength of a particle before measurement,
- p_1 is the momentum of a particle before measurement,
- λ_2 is the wavelength of a particle after measurement,
- p_2 is the momentum of a particle after measurement.

In other words, it is

$$\lambda_2 = \left(\frac{p_1}{p_2}\right) \cdot \lambda_1 \quad (79)$$

□

An act of measurement in quantum mechanics is nothing absolute and does not introduce any kind of uncertainty.

Example.

The measurement of the distance to faraway galaxies is primarily done using redshift, which refers to the shift of light from the galaxy towards the red end of the spectrum due to the expansion of the universe. By measuring the extent of this redshift, astronomers can determine how fast the galaxy is receding from us. The measurement of the distance to distant galaxies involves observing the light emitted by the galaxies themselves, rather than illuminating these galaxies with any artificial source. Astronomers use telescopes to capture the light that travels from these galaxies across the vastness of space to Earth. The galaxies electromagnetic wave (light) contains crucial information, such as the redshift, which indicates how much the light has stretched et cetera. By analyzing the redshift, astronomers can determine the galaxy's recession velocity and subsequently calculate its distance. This method relies solely on the natural light from the galaxies, making it possible to measure vast cosmic distances. This recession velocity, when used in conjunction with Hubble's Law, allows for the calculation of the galaxy's distance. Additionally, standard candles such as Type Ia supernovae, which have a known intrinsic brightness, are used to measure distances based on the observed brightness of these events. Since every moving quantum mechanical particle also generates a wave (see [Barukčić, 2013](#)), this wave can be measured by an apparatus without the measuring apparatus interacting with the particle or the wave itself. It depends more on the apparatus used than on the wave of a particle itself.

Energy and Time

Energy and time are fundamental concepts in physics that are intrinsically linked. Energy cannot be destroyed, a principle known as the conservation of energy. However, energy can transform and transfer over time.

Theorem 7 (Energy and Time). *In general, the relationship between energy and time can be expressed as:*

$$\frac{\ln(E_R)}{\ln(h)} + \frac{\ln(T)}{\ln(h)} = 1 \quad (80)$$

Proof by Direct Proof. We start with the axiom that $+1 = +1$, which is trivially true. Therefore, it is also true that:

$$+1 = +1 \quad (81)$$

Similarly, it holds that:

$$+h = +h \quad (82)$$

By considering the fundamental relationship in quantum mechanics, we know that:

$$f_R \cdot h = f_R \cdot h \quad (83)$$

From this, we derive the expression for energy:

$$E_R = f_R \cdot h \quad (84)$$

Multiplying equation 84 by the period of time T_R , it is

$$E_R \cdot T_R = f_R \cdot T_R \cdot h = h \quad (85)$$

Taking the natural logarithm of Equation 85, we obtain:

$$\ln(E_R) + \ln(T_R) = \ln(h) \quad (86)$$

Rearranging Equation 86, we have:

$$\frac{\ln(E_R)}{\ln(h)} + \frac{\ln(T_R)}{\ln(h)} = \frac{\ln(h)}{\ln(h)} = 1 \quad (87)$$

□

The principle that energy cannot be destroyed and must be conserved is known as **the law of conservation of energy** (see [von Mayer, 1842](#)). This fundamental concept in physics was first clearly formulated by Julius Robert von Mayer in 1842. Mayer, a German physician and physicist, recognized that energy is conserved in isolated systems and proposed that energy can change forms but the total amount of energy remains constant. Equation 80 challenges us to rethink our understanding of energy and its conservation. It suggests that we need to adopt a new viewpoint that goes beyond the traditional notions of energy being a static quantity. This equation implies a more dynamic interplay

between energy and time, prompting us to explore how energy can be both conserved and transformed in novel ways. The unity and the struggle of energy and time underscores the interconnectedness of both elements within an entity, emphasising that change as such is inherently determined. Energy transitions into time, and conversely, time transitions into energy, the reverse transformation occurs, both transitions are governed by the same fundamental natural laws. The interdependence of these transformations highlights the unity and coherence within something undergoing a transition. By reconsidering the fundamental principles underlying energy conservation, we can gain deeper insights into the complexities of physical systems and the nature of the universe itself. This new perspective encourages a more holistic understanding of the relationships between different physical quantities and their interactions over time.

Thought experiment: Objective Reality and Human Mind and Consciousness I

Theorem 8 (Objective Reality and Human Mind). *Objective reality exists independently of any human mind and consciousness.*

Proof by Contradiction. Assume the opposite of Theorem 8:
Objective reality does not exist independently of human mind and consciousness.

Nonetheless, scientists have demonstrated that dinosaurs lived during the Mesozoic era, which spanned from approximately 252 million to 66 million years ago. Dinosaurs existed on Earth during this period before suddenly becoming extinct at the end of the Cretaceous period.

However, there were neither humans nor human consciousness during this era for sure.

The assumption that objective reality does not exist independently of human mind and consciousness leads to a logical contradiction. Therefore, we must accept that objective reality does exist independently of any human mind and consciousness.

□

The hypothesis that objective reality does not exist without human mind and consciousness is simply incorrect and lacks any scientific validity.

Thought experiment: Objective Reality and Human Mind and Consciousness II

Theorem 9 (Objective Reality and Human Mind). *Objective reality exists independently of any human mind and consciousness.*

Proof by Contradiction. Let us assume the opposite of Theorem 9:
Objective reality does not exist independently of any human mind and consciousness.

A respected scientist named Platonsson holds the view that reality exists only dependent on human consciousness. He claims to have a proof to substantiate this view beyond doubt.

Unfortunately, Platonsson is infected by the Moivrevir1789 virus, resulting in his untimely demise before presenting his proof. Thus, the promised evidence cannot be provided.

Strangely, objective reality persists even though Platonsson's mind and consciousness no longer exists. This situation presents a logical contradiction. □

Imagine a scenario where individuals who believe that reality depends on human consciousness undergo a procedure removing their brains. This extreme test aims to challenge their theory by eliminating their ability to perceive and interpret objective reality. However, such measures are of course ethically problematic. Alternatively, consider engaging in thoughtful discussions with humans, scientists and thinkers who are sleeping, who passed away over five years ago or with those scientists and thinkers who, due to unfortunate circumstances, are brain dead or even with newborn children. What insights might their perspectives offer us on the relationship between human consciousness and the existence of objective reality? This thought experimental approach invites exploration into whether objective reality exists independently of human mind, consciousness and perception. In fact, the world continues to function, unaffected by individual lives, by any human mind, consciousness and perception. Seasons change, and natural laws persist regardless of human presence. This resilience highlights the autonomy of the universe, operating independently of human observation, human mind, consciousness and perception. Reflecting on how nature functions in the absence of human consciousness prompts deeper questions about the influence of human awareness on objective reality. The question of the fate of objective reality in the absence of human observers—whether through sleep, brain death, death, brain removal, or simply the non-existence of humans—prompts profound contemplation. During the time of the dinosaurs, there were unquestionably no humans or human consciousness, yet did the world exist then? Objective reality existed long before humans and their consciousness appeared, and it continues to exist independently and beyond human consciousness today. Objective reality will persist regardless of whether human consciousness is present or not. The moon orbits, stars shine, and physics laws endure irrespective of human presence, suggesting the world operates independently of human mind and consciousness. Such thought experiments challenge debates between realism and non-realism, probing the fundamental nature of existence beyond human perception.

4. Discussion

Heisenberg attempted to convince readers, using scientific tricks and unfair methods, that there is an inherent, natural limit to the precision with which the position and momentum of a particle can be simultaneously measured. With his uncertainty principle, Heisenberg aimed to demonstrate that this fundamental limit is linked to Planck's constant h , which dictates that it is impossible to determine both quantities with arbitrary accuracy. In the meantime, Heisenberg's uncertainty principle has been challenged and refuted from various perspectives.

Whether Heisenberg's uncertainty principle can still be salvaged by attributing an unknown Heisenberg's end of dreams factor $\tilde{\xi}$ to the term $\sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R)$ as

$$\tilde{\xi} \cdot \sigma(x_R) \cdot \sigma(p_R) = \frac{h}{4 \cdot \pi} \quad (88)$$

where $\sigma(x_R)$ and $\sigma(p_R)$ are the standard deviations (uncertainties) in position x_R and momentum p_R , remains a subject for further research.

5. Conclusion

Heisenberg's uncertainty relation,

$$\sigma(x) \cdot \sigma(p) \geq \frac{h}{4 \cdot \pi} \quad (89)$$

considered from various aspects, cannot be regarded as correct. Whether there are other, precise, deterministic formulations of the relationship between position and momentum might remain a subject for further research.

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Erratum

Unfortunately, some misprints appeared in the previous publications, especially in the section of definitions. Some of the misprints have been brought up to date in this publication as far as possible.

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I was born October, 1st 1961 in Novo Selo, Bosnia and Herzegovina, former Yugoslavia. I am of Croatian origin. From 1982-1989 C.E., I studied human medicine at the University of Hamburg, Germany. Meanwhile, I am working as a specialist of internal medicine. My basic field of research since my high school days at the Wirtschaftsgymnasium Bruchsal, Baden Württemberg, Germany is the mathematization of the relationship between a cause and an effect valid without any restriction under any circumstances including the conditions of classical logic, probability theory, quantum mechanics, special and general theory of relativity, human medicine et cetera. I endeavour to investigate positions of quantum mechanics, relativity theory, mathematics et cetera, only insofar as these positions put into question or endanger **the general validity of the principle of causality**.

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^m<https://portal.dnb.de/opac/showNextResultSite?currentResultId=%22Barukcic%22%26any&currentPosition=30>